

Adoption of fuzzy clustering techniques to determine the genetic characteristics of some dates varieties (proposed model)

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Abstract

Data mining analyzing amount of data to find relations among them and summarized for getting patterns like, graphical models, statistical models. and etc. These patterns are understandable and useful to their users by employing a range of automated extraction of knowledge from hideaways

This Research is a step to illustrate the concept of clustering technique in both theoretical and practical aspects. The theoretical side of the research dealt with the concept of data complexity and types, as well as an explanation of the algorithm (Fcm). The practical side applied the application of the nearest neighboring algorithm to determine the extent of convergence between some date varieties from the adoption of Fructose and and Glucose in Dates . The research concluded that the Fcm algorithm are easy and fast to clarify the genotypes of date species. We use Matlab R2013a to implement the practical side.

Keyword: Data mining, Clustering, Fuzzy clustering, Fuzzy C-Mean, Dates

I Introduction

The science of data mining aims to build graphical models, These models are algorithms or procedures...etc. The purpose of these models is to connect the inputs to obtain new knowledge based on the common characteristics between them, and thus benefit them in interpreting the results and making appropriate decisions. The Fcm algorithm is the best in classifying data fuzziness, The importance of research in the theoretical aspect is a modest contribution to the understanding of clustering concepts and Fuzzy clustering , And an explanation of the algorithm and the stages of Fcm. Different approaches to the problem of cluster analysis exist, such as: The modified fuzzy C-Mean method for clustering of microarray data[9]. A simple and fast method to determine the parameters for fuzzy C-Mean cluster analysis, Comparison of K-Means and Fuzzy c-Means Algorithm Performance for Automated Determination of the Arterial Input Function, An Improved Fuzzy C-Means Algorithm for the implementation of demand side management measure [11][17]

On the practical side we applied FCM algorithm to determine the extent of convergence between some date varieties from the adoption of Fructose and Glucose in Dates because they belong to more than one category at a time .We use Matlab R2013a to implement the practical side.

II Clustering :

Is a technique of data mining, the process of fragmentation of the original data into groups and collect

data with similar characteristics and put them in clusters depending on the measurement of distance between them, The purpose of this compilation is to construct descriptive models to facilitate the study of these models and to produce important and useful results for decision-makers.

The process of splitting the data into group depends on their sharing of similar properties. therfor the cluster is a group of similar data between them and are not similar to members belonging to other cluster[18].

To implement the clustering, pre-processing data should be performed as follows[16]:

Choose the cluster algorithm: Choose the appropriate algorithm that results from defining a good cluster chart for the data set.

- Evaluation of results: The results of the cluster algorithm are validated by appropriate techniques and standards, and cluster algorithms define previously unknown clusters, regardless of method, so the final fragmentation of the data requires certain types of assessment.
- Interpretation of results: Experience in the field of application needs to integrate cluster results with other proven and analyzed experiences in order to draw appropriate conclusions. Fig(1) illustrates the pre-Processing of data.
- method, so the final fragmentation of the data requires certain types of assessment.

Figure (1): illustrates the pre-Processing of data

III Types of clustering

The cluster is classified according to the criterion or criterion that defines the similarity between the elements of the data entered into the algorithm, as well as the theoretical and fundamental concepts on which the cluster analysis technique is based, for example, the fuzzy theory and statistics.

Clustering algorithms have evolved based on related topics such as data mining, automated learning, pattern recognition...etc, and these algorithms have been classified into the following categories[2][12][13] :

1. Hierarchical Clustering
2. Partitioned Clustering.
3. Clustering High Dimensional Data.
4. Clustering With Genetic Attributes.

Some researchers have classified clustering algorithms according to the method given in the definition of clusters to the following categories[3]:

1. Hierarchical Clustering.
2. Partitional Clustering.
3. Density-Based Clustering.
4. Grid-Based Clustering.

Each of the above varieties has sub-types and different algorithms to find clusters, so cluster algorithms can be classified according to the type of variables in the data as follows[7]:

Statistical Clustering: This type is based on the concepts of statistical analysis, and is used to measure the similarity of the fragmentation of models that are specified by numerical data.

-Conceptual Clustering: Used to clustered the Metadata, where models are modeled according to the concepts that carry rather than their values.

-Fuzzy Clustering: Specified techniques for cluster data, assuming that models can be grouped into more than one cluster, use The actual data uncertain (unreliable).

-Crisp Clustering: This type assumes a non-nested segmentation, meaning that the data point either belongs to the cluster or does not belong.

-Kohonen Net Clustering: Clustering in this type depends on the concepts of the neural network, and the cluster consists of external nodes.

IV Fuzzy Clustering

clustering is the process of data collection to explore their structures and commonalities, The fuzzy clustering technique allows objects to belong to several categories at the same time.

With different degrees of membership. In many cases, the data sets in the fuzzy clustered are more natural than the fixed aggregates, so that the organisms located on the boundary of the classes of classes are not necessarily bound to belong to one of the categories, But a membership rank of between 0 and 1 is assigned to each object to indicate its partial membership[5][6][10].

When trying to find graphic structures or models of data aggregates that are intertwined with each other and their complexity, one must consider the following[4]:

1. Data representation to convert data group cases into vectors of properties.
2. Use similarity measures. To approach the group of data sets.
- 3 - Hierarchical cluster algorithms are the basis for the structure of cluster algorithms, which divide the structure of data into smaller parts up to one single part. Stratified fuzzy cluster algorithms seek to create structures for data in which an

object is more than one class at a time and one of the most commonly used fuzzy clustering algorithms:

- ❖ Fuzzy Knn
- ❖ Weighted Knn
- ❖ Hcm

V Fcm algorithm

It is an iterative algorithm that divides data into groups based on the concept of Fuzzy membership. Instead of assigning each element to a single group, each element will have a different membership value for each group, so that the elements in the middle of the group have more membership value than those on the edges of the group, This algorithm attempts to identify the groups within the data by obtaining the smallest value of the sequence, which is useful when the required number of clusters is predetermined[15]; Thus, the algorithm attempts to place each point of data in a cluster. The probability (membership grade) of membership of a data point is calculated. Because absolute membership is not calculated, the algorithm is very fast because the number of duplicates required to achieve the specified aggregation match the required accuracy[1]

VI Implement the system

The Fuzzy cluster means that clusters belong to more than one species at a time, Thus, the idea of research has been developed by constructing a proposed model to find the distance between the two most important characteristics of dates, which are the ratios of fructose and glucose, the purpose of which is to estimate the number of clusters that will be based on the implementation of the algorithm Fcm [8].

VII specimen the study

In this research, 44 varieties of dates were selected, In this study, 44 varieties of date varieties were selected, which are produced in most Arab countries for the implementation of the model. They have properties such as fructose, glucose, sucrose,, etc. The fructose levels have been adopted because they are monounsaturated, easy to absorb, And does not need to absorb insulin from the pancreas to support the cluster, and determine the genetic characteristics of some dates varieties and table (1), which shows the dates of the research sample.

Table (1) : DATES VARIETIES WITH FRUCTOSE & GLUCOSE

#	Dates type	Glucose Rate	Fructose Rate
1	Sukkari	14.51	12.85
2	Sulaj	25.9	34.8
3	Shebebi	27.8	18.3
4	Meneifi	32.7	20.5
5	Shaishee	15.53	30.9
6	Safawi	37.5	20.6
7	Assela	32.18	25.3
8	Seqae	30.52	25.3
9	Ajwa	32.07	15.3
10	Anbara	32.7	20.5
11	Shaqla	29.67	21.07
12	Qatarah	32.3	30.9
13	Mabroom	32.07	20.08
14	Mjdool	27.5	34.33
15	Hulwah	31.3	28.6
16	Maktoumi	31.8	30.4
17	Barhi	29.23	20.5
18	Barni Madina	32.7	21.2
19	Romia	32.8	32
20	Abo al-kashab	30.8	30.2
21	Teeba	37.9	32.8
22	Khadyr	33.3	31.8
23	Khalas	32.15	18.3
24	Jamara	28.58	15.56
25	Um Kbare	31.45	32.8
26	Thawee	26.7	27.4
27	Rabeaa	30.09	28.7
28	Tabaeb	31.7	19.6
29	Rashadia	29.23	26.4
30	Ruthana	26.5	30.2
31	Sabala	30.35	25.5
32	Maktoumi	33	37.13
33	Molokia	35.81	15.08
34	Um kashab	35.3	34.5
35	Nabtat Ali	19.17	18
36	Sukkari Ahmer	14.96	11.36
37	Sukkari Asfer	21.7	19.8
38	Majnonna	40.4	36.5
39	Beraim	27.3	27
40	Nabtat Seif	22.27	21.2
41	Sanaf Kaber	31.4	29.4
42	Labane Hamra	33.7	22.3
43	Luna	41.2	36.5
44	Um Hamam	46.09	37.2

FIGURE (2) : DISTANCE BETWEEN FRUCTOSE & GLUCOSE RATIO OF DATE FRUITS

After obtaining the distance between the fructose and glucose ratios of the selected date, we arranged the results obtained from the ascending Knn algorithm, To determine the number of clusters to be adopted in the implementation sample of the Fcm algorithm, as shown in table (2) and Fig(3)

TABLE (2): THE ASCENDING SORTING OF DISTANCE & DETERMINATION THE CLUSTERS

Ascending Sorting	Dates type	distance	Dates type	#
20.73	Molokia	1.66	Sukkari	1.
16.90	Safawi	8.90	Sulaj	2.
16.77	Ajwa	9.50	Shebebi	3.
15.37	Shaishee	12.20	Meneifi	4.
13.85	Khalas	15.37	Shaishee	5.
13.02	Jamara	16.90	Safawi	6.
12.20	Meneifi	6.88	Assela	7.
12.20	Anbara	5.22	Seqae	8.
12.10	Tabaeb	16.77	Ajwa	9.
11.99	Mabroom	12.20	Anbara	10.
11.50	Barni Almadina	8.60	Shaqla	11.
11.40	Labane Hamraa	1.40	Qatarah	12.
9.50	Shebebi	11.99	Mabroom	13.
8.90	Sulaj	6.83	Medjool(mabool)	14.
8.89	UmAlhamam	2.70	Hulwa	15.
8.73	Barhi	1.40	Maktoumi	16.
8.60	Shaqla	8.73	Barhi	17.
6.88	Assela	11.50	Barni Almadina	18.
6.83	Medjool(mabool)	0.80	Romia	19.
5.22	Seqae	0.60	Abo Al kashab	20.
5.10	Teeba	5.10	Teeba	21.
4.85	Sabala	1.50	Khadyr	22.
4.70	Luna	13.85	Khalas	23.
4.13	Maktoumi	13.02	Jamara	24.
3.90	Majnonna	1.35	Um kbar	25.
3.70	Ruthana	0.70	Thawee	26.
3.60	Sukkari Ahmer	1.39	Rabeaa	27.
2.83	Rashadia	12.10	Tabaeb	28.
2.70	Hulwa	2.83	Rashadia	29.
2.00	Khabeez Variety	3.70	Ruthana	30.
1.90	SukkariAsfer	4.85	Sabala	31.
1.66	Sukkari	4.13	Maktoumi	32.
1.50	Khadyr	20.73	Molokia	33.
1.40	Maktoumi	0.80	Um kashab	34.
1.40	Qatarah	1.17	Nabtat Ali	35.
1.39	Rabeaa	3.60	Sukkari Ahmer	36.
1.35	Um Khar	1.90	Sukkari Asfer	37.
1.17	Nabtat Ali	3.90	Majnonna	38.
1.07	Nabtat Seif	0.30	Beraim	39.
0.80	Romia	1.07	Nabtat Seif	40.
0.80	Um Khashab	2.00	Khabeez Variety	41.
0.70	Thawee	11.40	Labane Hamraa	42.
0.60	Abo Al kashab	4.70	Luna	43.
0.30	Beraim	8.89	Um alhamam	44.

VIII Implement The distance between the Fructose

We will compute the distance between the fructose and glucose ratios according to equation (1) and Fig(2) Represents the result of executing the algorithm

$$d(i,j) = \sqrt{|x_i - x_j|^2} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE (3) : DETERMINE THE NO. OF CLUSTER AFTER ARRANGE

IX Implement Fcm algorithm[14][15]

After arranging the distance between the two properties ascending, we divided the data into 6 clusters to begin implementing the Fcm algorithm, The basis of its work is to divide the set of points $N=\{1,2,3,\dots X_m\}$ to a number of clusters, So that each point belongs to all clusters with different degrees of belonging. Each of these points has a special n (representing the number n dimension space). The idea of the algorithm is to minimize the target function in each frequency as shown in relation (2)

$$u_{ik} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^c \left(\frac{|x_k - c_i|}{|x_k - c_j|} \right)^{2/(m-1)}} \quad (2)$$

Where :

i:1,2,.....c.

c_i : represent the center of cluster (i).

The degree of x_j element membership can be determined by the cluster centered on C_i from the equation(3).

$$J(U, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_c) = \sum_{i=1}^c J_i = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{k=1}^n (u_{ik}^m)(d_{ik})^2 \quad (3)$$

FIGURE(4): DATES VARIETIES AFTER IMPLEMENTATION OF FCM ALGORITHM

IX Interpretation of results

Note from Figure (4) :

1. the fcm algorithm was wonderful in explain relations between different types of dates and is easy to implement and does not take a time.
2. symbols because the goal of the algorithm is to reduce the target function.
3. The class of kingship, is very different from the rest of the varieties and there is no common property between him and the varieties in the same cluster or with varieties

in other clusters, while the convergence of both Safawi and Ajwa with varieties of clusters 2 and 4.

4. The items in the fifth & sixth clusters shared in the qualities with the varieties in the clusters other than the Priem category, that is, it is possible to grow in most countries of the Arab countries.
5. The fifth cluster diverged most of the varieties, i.e. they do not share with the other clusters in genetic traits, that is, they can not be planted in areas other than Saudi
6. Most of the items in the third cluster whose genetic characteristics are similar to those of other clusters.

X Conclusion:

The observed results from the fcm algorithm showed that the algorithm was clear in determining the relationship between date types through the characteristics adopted in the research, and this algorithm is quick and easy in the application

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